

ELASTIC-VISCOPLASTIC HOMOGENIZATION ANALYSIS OF PLAIN-WOVEN GFRP LAMINATES WITH MISALIGNED PLAIN FABRICS

S. Kanamaru¹, T. Matsuda^{1*}

¹ Department of Engineering Mechanics and Energy, University of Tsukuba, Tsukuba, Japan

* Corresponding author (matsuda@kz.tsukuba.ac.jp)

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1 Introduction

Plain-woven laminates made of plain fabrics and polymer materials have high specific strength, high specific stiffness and good formability. They are therefore used in major industrial sectors, such as aerospace, auto and marine industries. This can make plain-woven laminates encounter severe conditions including high stress and high temperature. Thus, it is required to analyze not only elastic but also inelastic behavior of plain-woven laminates. In these kinds of analyses, the misalignment of plain fabrics in laminates, which is called "laminate misalignment" hereafter, becomes an important issue because such misalignment can affect the mechanical properties of plain-woven laminates [1-3]. Therefore, it is of great importance to investigate the effects of laminate misalignment on the mechanical properties of plain-woven laminates.

When analyzing mechanical properties of plain-woven laminates, the mathematical homogenization theory based on unit cell analysis [4] becomes one of the most useful theories. Therefore, this theory has been already applied to the elastic problems [5] and microscopic damage problems [6, 7]. In most studies, plain fabrics in plain-woven laminates were assumed to have no misalignment called "in-phase" laminate configuration, and unit cells were defined as shown in Fig. 1(a), resulting in no consideration for laminate misalignment. However, Takano et al. [1] conducted a microscopic damage analysis of plain-woven glass fiber-reinforced plastic (GFRP) laminates with not only in-phase but also "out-of-phase" laminate configurations. Here, the out-of-phase means that plain-woven fabrics possess half a unit cell misalignment as shown in Fig. 1(b). In this case, the unit cell becomes two times larger than that of in-phase as shown in the figure. Zeman and Šejnoha [2] further adopted quasi-quarter of a cell

Fig. 1 Two types of laminate configurations of plain fabrics; (a) in-phase (b) out-of-phase.

misalignment in addition to the two above-mentioned laminate configurations in a statistical investigation of the elastic properties of plain-woven carbon fiber-reinforced plastic (CFRP) laminates. Results of these analyses revealed significant influence of misalignment on the mechanical properties of plain-woven laminates. In the analyses, however, the misalignment was restricted to half or quasi-quarter of unit cells. In addition, the analyses for the misaligned cases required twice the volume of unit cells defined for aligned cases.

The authors [3,8-10], on the other hand, have performed elastic-viscoplastic and creep analyses of fiber-reinforced composites using a homogenization theory for non-linear time-dependent materials [11], which is referred to as "time-dependent homogenization theory" hereafter. In one of these studies [3], the authors proposed a method which was able to deal with both the in-phase and out-of-phase laminate configurations in plain-woven laminates using the same unit cell defined for the in-phase case, which was based on a point-symmetric boundary condition for unit cell analysis [12]. This method, however, was also limited to the half a cell misalignment, and was not able to deal with arbitrary misalignment.

In this study, elastic-viscoplastic behavior of plain-woven GFRP laminates with arbitrary laminate misalignment is analyzed using the time-dependent homogenization theory. In the analysis, the authors employ a basic cell, which is a quarter of an ordinary unit cell, as an analysis domain using a novel

boundary condition for unit cell analysis. This enables one basic cell to deal with arbitrary laminate misalignment, avoiding not only geometry and mesh generation of a basic cell for every misalignment, but also the influence of mesh dependence. From the analysis results, it is shown that the misalignment of plain fabrics affects viscoplastic properties of the plain-woven laminates.

2 Time-dependent homogenization theory for plain-woven laminates with misaligned plain fabrics

Consider a plain-woven laminate with misaligned plain fabrics as illustrated in Fig. 2. For the laminate, a basic cell A and Cartesian coordinates y_i ($i=1, 2, 3$) are defined as shown in the figure.

According to the conventional homogenization theory [4], the microscopic velocity field $\dot{u}_i(\mathbf{y}, t)$ in A is expressed as

$$\dot{u}_i(\mathbf{y}, t) = \dot{F}_{ij}(t)y_j + \dot{u}_i^\#(\mathbf{y}, t), \quad (1)$$

where $(\dot{})$ indicates differentiation with respect to t , $F_{ij}(t)$ denotes the macroscopic deformation gradient, and $\dot{u}_i^\#$ stands for the perturbed velocity from the macroscopic one $\dot{F}_{ij}(t)y_j$. Then the microscopic strain rate has the following expression:

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}(\mathbf{y}, t) = \dot{E}_{ij}(t) + \dot{\epsilon}_{ij}^\#(\mathbf{y}, t), \quad (2)$$

where \dot{E}_{ij} and $\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}^\#$ indicate respectively the macroscopic strain rate and the perturbed strain rate described as $\dot{E}_{ij} = (\dot{F}_{ij} + \dot{F}_{ji})/2$ and $\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}^\# = (\dot{u}_{i,j}^\# + \dot{u}_{j,i}^\#)/2$, in which $()_{,j}$ represents the differentiation with

Fig. 2 Plain-woven laminate with misaligned plain fabrics. In the figure, a and b indicate the amount of misalignment in the y_1 - and y_2 -directions, respectively.

respect to y_j .

The equilibrium of σ_{ij} is expressed in a rate form as

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij,j} = 0. \quad (3)$$

Let $v_i(\mathbf{y}, t)$ be an arbitrary variation of the perturbed velocity field $\dot{u}_i^\#$ defined in A at t . Then, the integration by parts and the divergence theorem allow Eq. (3) to be transformed to a weak form:

$$\int_A \dot{\sigma}_{ij} v_{i,j} dA - \int_\Gamma \dot{\sigma}_{ij} n_j v_i d\Gamma = 0, \quad (4)$$

where Γ signifies the boundary of A , and n_j indicates the unit vector outward normal to Γ .

Now, Γ is divided into Γ_α ($\alpha=1, 2, \dots, 12$) as shown in Fig. 3. Then, the integral term in the above equation can be expressed as

$$\int_\Gamma \dot{\sigma}_{ij} n_j v_i d\Gamma = \sum_\alpha \int_{\Gamma_\alpha} \dot{\sigma}_{ij} n_j v_i d\Gamma_\alpha. \quad (5)$$

First, on Γ_1 , the distributions of $\dot{u}_i^\#$, i.e. v_i , and $\dot{\sigma}_{ij}$ are point-symmetric with respect to its center, because the internal structure satisfies point-symmetry regarding the point. Therefore, the boundary integral term for Γ_1 vanishes, i.e.:

$$\int_{\Gamma_1} \dot{\sigma}_{ij} n_j v_i d\Gamma_1 = 0. \quad (6)$$

The same situation exists on $\Gamma_3, \Gamma_5, \Gamma_7$ and $\Gamma_9 - \Gamma_{12}$. Thus, we have

$$\int_{\Gamma_3} \dot{\sigma}_{ij} n_j v_i d\Gamma_3 = 0, \quad (7)$$

$$\int_{\Gamma_5} \dot{\sigma}_{ij} n_j v_i d\Gamma_5 = 0, \quad (8)$$

$$\int_{\Gamma_7} \dot{\sigma}_{ij} n_j v_i d\Gamma_7 = 0, \quad (9)$$

Fig. 3 Boundaries Γ_α ($\alpha=1, 2, \dots, 12$) of the basic cell; (a) upper surface, (b) bottom surface and (c) side surfaces.

$$\sum_{\alpha=9}^{12} \int_{\Gamma_\alpha} \dot{\sigma}_{ij} n_j v_i d\Gamma_\alpha = 0. \quad (10)$$

By contrast, v_i and $\dot{\sigma}_{ij}$ on Γ_2 and those on Γ_8 respectively distribute periodically, while n_j takes the opposite directions on these boundaries. In consequence, the following relation is obtained:

$$\int_{\Gamma_2} \dot{\sigma}_{ij} n_j v_i d\Gamma_2 + \int_{\Gamma_8} \dot{\sigma}_{ij} n_j v_i d\Gamma_8 = 0. \quad (11)$$

The same situation on Γ_4 and Γ_6 yields

$$\int_{\Gamma_4} \dot{\sigma}_{ij} n_j v_i d\Gamma_4 + \int_{\Gamma_6} \dot{\sigma}_{ij} n_j v_i d\Gamma_6 = 0, \quad (12)$$

Substitution of Eqs. (6)-(12) into Eq. (5) leads to

$$\sum_\alpha \int_{\Gamma_\alpha} \dot{\sigma}_{ij} n_j v_i d\Gamma_\alpha = 0, \quad (13)$$

which allows Eq. (4) to be written as

$$\int_A \dot{\sigma}_{ij} v_{i,j} dA = 0. \quad (14)$$

This resulting equation has the same form as that obtained in the original work by Ohno et al. [11], which enables the authors to rebuild the time-dependent homogenization theory as follows.

Constituents of the material are assumed to exhibit linear elasticity and non-linear viscoplasticity as characterized by

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = c_{ijkl} (\dot{\epsilon}_{kl} - \beta_{kl}), \quad (15)$$

where c_{ijkl} and β_{kl} represent the elastic stiffness and viscoplastic strain rate of the constituents, satisfying $c_{ijkl} = c_{jikl} = c_{ijlk} = c_{klij}$ and $\beta_{kl} = \beta_{lk}$. Substitution of the above equation and Eq. (2) into Eq. (14) results in

$$\int_A c_{ijpq} \dot{u}_{p,q}^\# v_{i,j} dA = -\dot{E}_{kl} \int_A c_{ijkl} v_{i,j} dA + \int_A c_{ijkl} \beta_{kl} v_{i,j} dA. \quad (16)$$

Let χ_i^{kl} and φ_i be functions which are determined by solving the following boundary value problems for A , respectively [11]:

$$\int_A c_{ijpq} \chi_{p,q}^{kl} v_{i,j} dA = -\int_A c_{ijkl} v_{i,j} dA, \quad (17)$$

$$\int_A c_{ijpq} \varphi_{p,q} v_{i,j} dA = \int_A c_{ijkl} \beta_{kl} v_{i,j} dA. \quad (18)$$

Then Eq. (16) has the following solution for the perturbed velocity field:

$$\dot{u}_i^\#(\mathbf{y}, t) = \chi_i^{kl}(\mathbf{y}) \dot{E}_{kl}(t) + \varphi_i(\mathbf{y}, t). \quad (19)$$

By substituting Eq. (2) and the above equation into Eq. (15), the evolution equation of microscopic stress σ_{ij} and the relation between macroscopic stress rate $\dot{\Sigma}_{ij}^\#$ and strain rate \dot{E}_{kl} are derived [11]:

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = c_{ijpq} (\delta_{pk} \delta_{ql} + \chi_{p,q}^{kl}) \dot{E}_{kl} - c_{ijkl} (\beta_{kl} - \phi_{k,l}), \quad (20)$$

$$\dot{\Sigma}_{ij} = \langle c_{ijpq} (\delta_{pk} \delta_{ql} + \chi_{p,q}^{kl}) \rangle \dot{E}_{kl} - \langle c_{ijkl} (\beta_{kl} - \phi_{k,l}) \rangle, \quad (21)$$

where δ_{ij} indicates Kronecker's delta, $\langle \rangle$ stands for the volume average in A defined as $\langle \# \rangle = |A|^{-1} \int_A \# dA$, in which $|A|$ signifies the volume of A .

It is emphasized that the present theory enables one basic cell to be sufficient to deal with arbitrary misalignment by changing the area ratios of $\Gamma_1 - \Gamma_8$.

3 Analysis conditions

In the present analysis, the laminate misalignment in the y_1 - and y_2 -directions were considered as illustrated in Fig. 4. Denoting the amount of misalignment in the y_1 - and y_2 -directions as a and b , respectively, eight cases of their combinations were selected, i.e. $a-b = 0-0, 0-l/4, 0-l/2, 0-3l/4, 0-l, l/4-l/4, l/2-l/2$ and $l-l$, where l indicates the width and depth of the basic cell. The basic cell was defined and divided into eight-node isoparametric elements (2048 elements, 2499 nodes) as shown in Fig. 5. The fiber bundles were regarded as transversely isotropic elastic materials, while the epoxy matrix as an isotropic elastic-viscoplastic material. Material properties used are shown in Table. 1 [3]. The plain-woven laminates were subjected to a macroscopic uniaxial load at a constant strain rate of $10^{-5} s^{-1}$ at room temperature. Three cases of loading directions, i.e. the y_1 -, y_2 - and 45° -directions, were considered.

Fig. 4 Laminate misalignment.

Fig. 5 Basic cell of plain-woven GFRP laminates and its finite element mesh; (a) full view and (b) fiber bundles in the basic cell.

Table 1. Material constants of glass fibers and epoxy

Glass fiber	$E_f = 80.0 \times 10^3$	$\nu_f = 0.30$	
Epoxy	$E_m = 5.0 \times 10^3$	$\nu_m = 0.35$	$\dot{\epsilon}_0^p = 10^{-5}$
	$g(\bar{\epsilon}^p) = (\bar{\epsilon}^p)^{0.50} + 24.5/2.5^{\bar{\epsilon}^p}$		$n = 20$

4 Results of analysis

Figures 6-8 show the macroscopic stress-strain relations of the plain-woven laminates subjected to the uniaxial tension in the y_1 -, y_2 - and 45° -directions, respectively. First, it is seen from Fig. 6 that, with loading in the y_1 -direction, the flow stress varies depending on the laminate misalignment, and the flow stress for $a-b=0-l$ is about 30% higher than that for $0-0$ at $E_{11}=0.02$, showing a significant influence of laminate misalignment on the macroscopic viscoplastic behavior of the laminates. With the y_2 -direction loading, the change of flow stress is also confirmed in Fig. 7. In this case, the flow stresses for $a-b=0-l$ and for $0-0$ also become the maximum and minimum values, respectively.

When loaded in the 45° -direction, on the other hand, the laminates exhibited much more viscoplastic nonlinearity (Fig. 8) than that observed in the on-axis loading mentioned above. This was because the viscoplasticity of the epoxy matrix became dominant in off-axis loading due to shear deformation of the laminates [3], meaning that the deformation mechanism was quite different from that of the on-axis loading. Nevertheless, the laminate misalignment also affects the flow stress of the laminates as shown in Fig. 8. It should be noted however that the flow stress decreases with the increase of laminate misalignment, in contrast to the on-axis loading.

Fig. 6 Macroscopic stress-strain relations of the plain-woven GFRP laminates with laminate misalignment subjected to uniaxial loading in the y_1 -direction.

Fig. 7 Macroscopic stress-strain relations of the plain-woven GFRP laminates with laminate misalignment subjected to uniaxial loading in the y_2 -direction.

Fig. 8 Macroscopic stress-strain relations of the plain-woven GFRP laminates with laminate misalignment subjected to uniaxial loading in the 45° -direction.

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